

STRUCTURAL ELEMENTS AND PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE "VERSATILE" METHODOLOGY

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Abstract. *The article scientifically highlights the pedagogical foundations, structural elements, and effectiveness of the "Versatile" methodology in developing productive communication skills in English among preschool preparation group children. It is emphasized that the methodology aligns with children's natural language acquisition process due to its basis in play, musical-motor, and role-play activities.*

Keywords: *"Versatile", methodology and stages, games, activities.*

Introduction

Today, in the preschool education system, the process of teaching foreign languages, particularly English, is implemented based on children's age characteristics, psychological needs, and natural activity – learning through play. At the preschool preparation age, the formation of productive communication skills, i.e., developing skills such as independent speaking, constructing dialogues, responding appropriately to situations, and being able to ask questions, is of particular importance.

Teaching language through natural, engaging, active, and meaningful activities is one of the main requirements of the communicative-educational approach. The "Versatile" methodology, developed for this purpose, creates a multimodal learning environment for children and engages them in the active communication process.

"Versatile" is implemented by employing methods of natural language acquisition for children. According to this approach, a child, during the process of acquiring their native language, independently understands the content of utterances and gradually masters them by reacting to these phrases. This process, continued over a certain period, leads to the child speaking independently – entering into the communication process. This very situation is the main principle of the "Versatile" method, serving to ensure that children can freely enter into communication in a foreign language by giving various commands, teaching language through demonstrating actions, and using short poems and cheerful songs.

The main goal of the methodology is the gradual development of productive communication skills in English in preschool preparation age children through the integration of games, action songs, poems, and role-play activities.

As the tasks of this methodology, we can cite the following:

1.To determine the linguodidactic potential of the interactive activities included in the methodology's foundation.

2.To form children's skills in listening comprehension, quick response, and engaging in dialogic speech.

3.To create opportunities for remembering lexical units and using them in active speech.

4.To ensure motivation for language learning and a positive emotional environment.

5.To scientifically substantiate the effectiveness of the methodology during the experimental process.

The "Versatile" methodology, aimed at developing productive communication skills in English among preschool preparation group children, is distinguished by its content-rich and formally diverse structural elements. Each component of the methodology is based on specific pedagogical-psychological foundations and is designed in accordance with children's age characteristics, ensuring that their language acquisition process occurs naturally and effectively.

Below, the main structural elements of the methodology are detailed, along with their pedagogical foundations, practical application, and developmental functions.

1. "Zukkojon says" Game (Command-Based Action Game)

The "Zukkojon says" game is an adapted version of the "Total Physical Response (TPR)" method for preschool-aged children. Psycholinguistically, this game is based on the child's native language acquisition process: just as a child learning their native language listens to adults' commands and responds with physical actions, the same mechanism is activated during the English language learning process.

According to the TPR method developed by American psycholinguist James Asher, listening comprehension plays a primary role in the initial stage of language learning. Before engaging in speech activity, the child learns to understand the language by listening to it for a certain period. This process is called the "incubation period." The "Zukkojon says" game accelerates children's transition from passive language acquisition to active use precisely during this period.

According to Stephen Krashen's "comprehensible input" theory, language learners need language material that is slightly above their current level but still understandable. The commands given in the "Zukkojon says" game (e.g., "Touch your nose," "Jump," "Sit down") are simple, clear, and related to actions, making them comprehensible to children.

During the game, the instructor gives commands such as "Zukkojon says: touch your head." Children perform only those commands preceded by the phrase "Zukkojon says." If this phrase is not stated, the command should not be performed.

This develops children's concentration, listening comprehension, and quick response skills.

2. *"Cheerful and lively songs" — Action Songs*

The combination of music and movement is an important factor in children's language acquisition process. Neurolinguistic research shows that music activates both hemispheres of the brain: the right hemisphere receives rhythm and melody, while the left hemisphere processes words and their meanings. This leads to more solid acquisition of language material.

According to the "code switching" theory, learning language through music and movement is an effective tool in forming the foundations of bilingualism in children. Also, according to the principle of "multisensory learning," when a child acquires language through hearing, seeing, and moving simultaneously, neural connections are strengthened.

In the "Versatile" methodology, popular children's songs such as "If you're happy," "Head, shoulders, knees and toes," and "Walking walking" are used. Each song is dedicated to a specific topic (body parts, animals, actions, family), and children perform actions corresponding to the lyrics. For example, in the song "Rain, rain, go away," children make movements representing raindrops.

3. *"Action Poems" — Poems with Movement*

The combination of poetry and movement plays an important role in developing children's rhythmic speech. Action poems, also called "chants" or "rhymes," develop children's phonemic hearing, speech breathing, and articulation.

According to Lev Vygotsky's "zone of proximal development" theory, tasks that a child performs with adult help or cooperation prepare the ground for their independent development. During action poems, the instructor recites the poem, and children follow, repeating the words along with the actions. Gradually, children progress to reciting the poems independently.

In the "Versatile" methodology, short and rhythmic poems such as "Two little dicky birds," "Five little monkeys," and "I'm a little teapot" are used. Each poem contains specific thematic and lexical material. For example, through the poem "Two little dicky birds," numbers, bird names, and verbs like "fly away" are acquired.

4. *"Finger doll" — Role-Play Game (Play with Finger Puppets)*

Role-play games are the leading activity of preschool-aged children. Role-play games conducted with finger puppets are important tools in developing children's social speech, dialogic communication, and creative thinking.

According to Lev Vygotsky's "social learning" theory, a child acquires language and social skills through communication and cooperation with people around them. Through play, the child experiments with different social roles, models real-life situations, and learns to communicate. Jean Piaget emphasized the importance of symbolic play in the development of a child's thinking.

Within the "Finger doll" method, the instructor creates various plot-based situations using finger puppets (family members, animals, professionals). Children put the puppets on their fingers, speak on their behalf, construct dialogues, and ask and answer questions. For example, role-play games are organized on topics such as "Doctor and patient," "Shop," and "Family."

5. *"Fly swatter" Game*

The "Fly swatter" game is an interactive game that combines visual and kinesthetic learning methods. It serves to develop children's concentration, quick thinking, and lexical activation skills.

From a cognitive psychology perspective, this game develops "reaction time" and "word retrieval" processes. Also, according to the principle of "game-based learning," children acquire language material more quickly and easily due to competition and interest during the game.

For the game, thematic pictures (animals, fruits, colors, toys) are attached to the wall or board. Children are given a fly swatter. The instructor says a word in English (e.g., "apple"), and children must hit the picture corresponding to that word with the fly swatter. In a more complex version of the game, the instructor shows a picture, and children say its name and hit the picture.

The practical application of the "Versatile" methodology with preschool preparation group children directly requires the development of a research methodology and its implementation stages designed for this methodology.

Accordingly, the following stages are outlined:

1. Diagnostic Stage:

-Diagnostics of children's initial communication skills (observation, conversation, control tasks).

-Studying the psycholinguistic foundations of the English language teaching process.

-Forming experimental and control groups for the research.

2.Experimental-Testing Stage:

-Regular sessions were organized based on the 5 methods of the "Versatile" methodology.

-During each session, children's activity in initiating communication, changes in speech tempo, and the dynamics of lexical development were observed.

-Interdisciplinary integration (music, visual arts, physical education) was applied.

3.Control and Evaluation Stage:

-The learning outcomes of the experimental and control groups were compared.

-Results were analyzed through observation logs, audiovisual recordings, and tests.

-The didactic significance of the approach was assessed through methodological evaluation by experts.

Conducting work based on these stages and implementing sessions using the "Versatile" methodology leads to the following results:

1.Skills in constructing simple dialogues in English, engaging in conversation, and asking and answering questions are strengthened.

2.The ability to expand lexical wealth and use it in context is formed.

3.Pronunciation, rhythm, intonation, and speech culture improve.

4.Children's confidence in initiating communication and expressing their thoughts increases.

5.The pace of acquisition increases based on a natural language environment, multimodal methods, and active participation.

The structural elements of the "Versatile" methodology have been developed based on children's age characteristics, psychological needs, and natural types of activity. Each element is founded on specific pedagogical-psychological theories and performs unique developmental functions:

- "Zukkojon says" – language acquisition through listening comprehension and physical response;

- Action songs – development of musical-rhythmic and phonetic skills;
- Action poems – multisensory learning and memory strengthening;
- Finger puppets – formation of dialogic speech and social communication;
- "Fly swatter" – lexical activation and development of quick thinking.

According to the research results, the "Versatile" methodology creates an adapted, playful, active, and emotionally rich learning environment for children and effectively develops productive communication skills in English. The methodology is formed based on the requirements of the communicative approach and aligns with the linguodidactic principles of natural language learning.

Games enhance children's involvement in speech activities; musical-motor activities develop phonetic and rhythmic competence; and role-play activities expand the meaningful direction of communication. As a result, the level of children's active, independent, and meaningful engagement in communication in English significantly increases.

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